

Characterizing Sensory Adaptation to Transcutaneous Electrical Nerve Stimulation: Implications for Stable Tactile Feedback in Neuroprosthetics

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Abstract— This study aimed to characterize peripheral nervous system adaptation to transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS), focusing on the temporal dynamics of perceived intensity decay at different stimulation frequencies. Six healthy volunteers received constant electrical stimulation to the ring finger of the left hand in two experimental blocks at 10 Hz and 20 Hz, with current intensity individually adjusted to 80% of each participant’s pain threshold and a pulse-width of 500 μ s. Perceived intensity was rated every 15 seconds over 180 seconds, and the resulting data were fitted to a piecewise exponential decay model to extract delay (d), decay amplitude (A), and time constant (τ). Median delays were 8.47 s for 10 Hz and 19.33 s for 20 Hz. No significant linear relationships were found between stimulation frequency and either delay or decay amplitude; however, a non-significant trend toward higher τ values was observed at 20 Hz ($p = 0.27$). Results revealed marked interindividual variability in adaptation onset and magnitude, in agreement with prior literature on both invasive and noninvasive stimulation. These findings reinforce the need for personalized and temporally dynamic stimulation protocols to maintain stable perceptual intensity in prolonged tactile feedback applications, particularly in the context of upper-limb prosthetic control.

Keywords— Sensory adaptation, TENS, tactile feedback, neuroprosthetics.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tactile sensations are essential for human beings to understand and interact with the world around them [1], [2].

Through touch, it is possible to perceive different levels of pressure, compliance and textures [3], [4]. It is an important form of sensorial perception, since a significant portion of the interaction with the environment involves touch. The absence of tactile response compromises the precision and dexterity of movements, hindering daily activities [5], [6]. In this context, implementing tactile sensations in prosthetic models significantly improves user adaptation by restoring a sense of touch that was once lost [6]. Therefore, it is of paramount importance to understand how tactile systems work, in order to enable its artificial replication as faithfully and accurately as possible.

The tactile system is responsible for detecting mechanical stimuli on the skin and transforming them into neural signals that are interpreted by the brain [7], [8]. This process begins with the mechanoreceptors, which are responsible for the mechanotransduction of these stimuli [8].

Physiologically there are four types of mechanoreceptors that can be classified by the stimuli adaptation time [8]. Rapidly adapting sensors, such as Meissner and Pacini’s corpuscles, respond mainly to onset and offset of stimuli, making them ideal for detecting sudden changes in the environment. In contrast, slowly adapting receptors, such as Merkel’s disks and Ruffini’s corpuscles, maintain their activities as long as the stimuli is present, contributing to continuous perception of pressure and shape. Those mechanoreceptors are innervated by A β nerve fibers, which have a high conduction velocity and are responsible for

transmitting sensory information to the central nervous system [8].

The application of constant mechanical stimuli on the skin leads to progressive perceptual and neuronal desensitization, known as accommodation or desensitization of these nerve fibers, caused by a gradual increase in their spike generation threshold [9]. This accommodation can be partly explained by mechanoreceptors adaptation [10]. The same phenomenon occurs when electrical stimuli is applied to the skin, limiting the use of transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS) for the restoration of tactile sensation in prosthesis users [9].

TENS has proven to be a viable alternative for tactile restoration, as it can evoke different modalities of sensation, such as touch, tingling and vibration, by modulating electrical pulses that stimulate sensory nerve fibers in the skin, thereby simulating the transmission of tactile signals to the brain [10], [11], [12]. Therefore, characterizing sensory adaptation to electrical stimulation is essential for the development of adaptive tactile restoration models capable of overcoming this limitation [12], since accommodation markedly impairs the restored tactile perception, causing the user to lose the induced sensation within a short period of time [9].

For this reason, the aim of this study is to characterize the adaptation of the peripheral nervous system under transcutaneous stimulation, assessing the percentage variation in perceived intensity and its temporal course as a function of the electrostimulation frequency.

II. METHODS

This research received approval from the Research Ethics Committee of the Federal University of Uberlândia, with ethical approval number: 82612724.4.0000.5152.

A. Subjects

Six healthy able-bodied volunteers participated in the experiment, 4 of whom were female, with an average age of 25.5 ± 3.1 years. Throughout the experiment, volunteers remained seated comfortably with their left arm extended and resting on a table, and two square electrodes measuring approximately 2 cm^2 were placed on the ring finger of the left hand, with the anode electrode positioned on the most distal phalanx (Fig. 1).

B. Electrical Stimuli

The stimuli delivered to subjects through non-invasive electrode were provided by a programmable TENS in square,

bi-phasic, balanced, current-controlled, cathode-first pulses [13], [14].

C. Experimental protocol

After placing the electrodes, the pain threshold was verified to define the stimulus current delivered to each volunteer. In this stage, a pulse width of $500 \mu\text{s}$ and a frequency of 20 Hz were used, the highest frequency used during the experimental protocol. The stimulation current was increased in increments of 0.1 mA, starting at 0.2 mA, until the volunteer reported the onset of discomfort. This process was performed in triplicate with 2-minute intervals between each trial to avoid individual adaptation. The current used was 80% of the average of the three trials, ensuring safe and comfortable stimulation with a well-defined perceived intensity.

Fig. 1 – Experimental setup containing stimuli features, time to intensity rating and the TENS electrode positioning

After defining the stimulation current, each volunteer participated in two experimental blocks with different stimulation frequencies designed to assess nerve adaptation to constant electrostimulation. The block consisted of the

presentation of a constant electrical conditioning stimulus for an uninterrupted duration of 3 minutes (180 seconds), with a fixed pulse width of 500 μ s and frequencies of 10 Hz, Block 1, and 20 Hz, Block 2. A five-minute interval was imposed between experimental blocks to allow for complete recovery from adaptation [9].

During constant stimulation, every 15 seconds, participants were asked to rate the intensity of the sensation they perceived (Fig. 1). Volunteers were instructed to express the magnitude of the perceived intensity on a numerical scale, where the sensation at the beginning of the stimulus presentation was considered equal to 10, whereas 0 represented the absence of perception of the stimulus.

D. Data Analysis

The mean magnitudes reported during the sessions were expressed as a percentage of the initially perceived intensity magnitude. The percentage of perceived intensity as a function of time was adjusted by a piecewise function [9], defined as:

$$I(t) = \begin{cases} 100\%, & t < d \\ A \cdot e^{\left(\frac{-(t-d)}{\tau}\right)} + (100 - A), & t \geq d \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- $I(t)$ is the intensity perceived at time t .
- A is the amplitude of the intensity decay (in percentage).
- τ is the time constant of decay (in seconds).
- d is the delay between the onset of the stimulus and the onset of the decay of the intensity of the sensation.

The variables A , τ and d are the parameters to be adjusted. The first part of piecewise function ($t < d$) is a constant, characterized by the delay in sensitivity decay and represents the conservation of the magnitude of the intensity initially perceived. The second part describes the exponential decay behavior considering the delay of the first part of the function, expressed as a percentage. The curve was adjusted using a non-linear least squares method implemented in Python, with the *curve_fit* function of the *scipy.optimize* module.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) was calculated to assess the accuracy of the data fit, and the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was used to quantify the influence of frequency on specific curve features.

II. RESULTS

The parameters obtained from the curve fitting were analyzed separately. As shown in Fig. 2, for the 10 Hz frequency, the median delay (d) for the decay in perceived intensity among participants was 8.47 s (interquartile range (IQR) = [6.29, 30.61]), and 19.33 s (IQR = [3.49, 28.00]) for the 20 Hz frequency.

Fig. 2 – Boxplot of median and interquartile range (IQR) delay (d) values for the decay of perceived intensity at 10 Hz and 20 Hz. The dark blue solid line indicates the median, the box edges indicate the first (25%) and third (75%) quartiles, and the ends of the dashed lines represent the minimum and maximum data

To analyze the percentage decay of perceived intensity singly, the data were paired such that $t = d$ for all participants. This curve fitting approach enabled the assessment of the time course of sensory adaptation to TENS for each volunteer, as well as the R^2 coefficient for each curve fit. These data, along with the features extracted from the median data across all participants, are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 – Median values of delay (d), percentage decay amplitude (A), time constant (τ), and R^2 from curve fitting, aggregated by stimulation frequency

Frequency Feature	10 Hz			20 Hz		
	τ (s)	A (%)	R^2	τ (s)	A (%)	R^2
Subject 1	92.32	100	0.97	88.38	100	0.94
Subject 2	29.21	79.51	0.94	48.79	69.88	0.79
Subject 3	23.69	68.31	0.77	47.87	96.99	0.97
Subject 4	22.14	72.73	0.84	37.83	55.22	0.84
Subject 5	101.80	99.68	0.97	176.3	100	0.90
Subject 6	28.96	63.96	0.80	40.55	83.82	0.89
Median	35.8	74.14	0.91	50.17	74.27	0.89

Additionally, the median of the data aggregated by frequency allowed visualization of the decay trend in perceived intensity for 10 Hz (Fig. 3a) and for 20 Hz (Fig. 3b), both plotted alongside the original data from each subject.

The Pearson correlation coefficient was used to investigate whether different frequencies exert any influence on the free parameters of the curve fitting, revealing no significant linear relationship with either the decay amplitude (A, $r = -0.01$, $p = 0.96$) or the observed delay (d, $r = 0.02$, $p = 0.95$). Conversely, a weak linear proportionality was indicated between stimulation frequency and the time constant of the perceived intensity decay (τ) ($r = 0.34$, $p = 0.27$).

Fig. 3 – Median percentage decay in perceived intensity over time for (a) 10 Hz and (b) 20 Hz, plotted alongside individual participant data. Curves in solid red lines represent the fit of the exponential decay model

III. DISCUSSION

The results of the present study showed that transcutaneous electrical stimulation at frequencies of 10 Hz and 20 Hz induced a perceptible decay in sensation intensity over time in all participants (Fig. 3). This behavior is consistent with the phenomenon of sensory adaptation

described by [9], [15], in which electrical stimulation (invasive and non-invasive, respectively) resulted in a progressive reduction in perceived magnitude over time, followed by partial recovery after stimulus interruption.

Interindividual variability was observed in the delay and decay rate parameters of perceived intensity (Fig. 2), similar to that reported by [9], [15], who noted that such differences may stem from variability in the excitability of the recruited fibers and differences in central processing. This observation aligns with the proposal of [16], who emphasizes the need for personalized approaches to sensory encoding in tactile feedback systems in order to account for each individual's specific responses.

Although no significant linear relationship was found between stimulation frequency and the delay or decay amplitude parameters, a trend toward a higher time constant (τ) was observed for 20 Hz compared to 10 Hz ($p = 0.27$, not statistically significant). In a study by [17], the authors showed that perceived intensity is related to the activation charge rate (ACR), a metric that integrates charge per pulse and frequency. However, in a subsequent study by the same group [9], no significant correlation was found between invasive stimulation frequency and adaptation parameters such as delay and decay rate, indicating that while the ACR may predict initial perception, it does not necessarily reflect adaptive behavior over time. These differences highlight the need to include a larger number of participants in the present study to increase the statistical power of the analyses, thereby enabling a more reliable assessment of whether this trend can be confirmed for TENS.

The presence of adaptation, observed within the first seconds of stimulation in some participants, is consistent with the quantitative characterization reported by [15], who found that the onset and rate of adaptation varied among individuals under constant-intensity stimulation. One possible approach to modifying certain characteristics of sensory adaptation (i.e., percentage amplitude and time constant of perceived intensity decay) involves temporal adjustments to stimulation parameters, as such adjustments can modulate perceived intensity over time, as indicated by [18].

Overall, the findings of this study corroborate existing literature by demonstrating that prolonged electrical stimulation of nerves is subject to perceptual adaptation, with substantial variation in magnitude and onset latency between individuals. These results reinforce the importance of stimulation strategies that combine parametric personalization and temporal variation, taking individual responses into account to preserve perceived intensity in prolonged tactile feedback applications for upper-limb prostheses.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The present study demonstrated that transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation at frequencies of 10 Hz and 20 Hz induces a progressive decay in perceived intensity in healthy individuals, regardless of the frequency used. Although a trend toward a higher time constant was observed for 20 Hz, no statistically significant differences were found between the tested conditions. The interindividual variability in delay and decay rate parameters confirms previous findings and underscores the need for personalized protocols to optimize perceptual stability.

These results corroborate evidence from the literature that perceptual adaptation is a robust aspect of TENS, indicating that dynamic and individualized stimulation strategies are essential for preserving sensation intensity over long-term applications. In contexts of tactile feedback for prosthetics, implementing such strategies may be crucial for improving perceptual consistency and functional performance.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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